

ON THE MECHANISM OF THE REACTION IN THE FORMATION OF THE BLUE PEROXYCHROMIC ACID

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It has been found that the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid is not an acid but a chromium perchromate. The mechanism suggested is that due to the addition of H_2O_2 to $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution, $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ is oxidised to $Cr_2O_{10}^{2-}$ and simultaneously due to the presence of hydrogen ions, H_2O_2 reduces $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ to Cr^{3+} , and this Cr^{3+} combines with $Cr_2O_{10}^{2-}$ to form chromium perchromate. In order to show the validity of this reaction, the blue peroxychromic acid has been prepared with $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution, H_2O_2 and chromium sulphate solution without the presence of any acid.

Barreswil (*Compt. rend.*, 1848, 16, 1085) observed that when an acidified solution of potassium dichromate was treated with hydrogen peroxide, 4 mols. of oxygen were given off per mol. of $K_2Cr_2O_7$, and he assumed that the peroxychromic acid, $Cr_2O_7H_2O$, was formed as an intermediate product. Aschoff (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1860, 81, 402; *Chem. News*, 1862, 5, 129) represented the reaction as :

followed by

Fairley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 31, 1, 125) assumed that the intermediate peroxychromic acid was CrO_6H_2O . Martinon (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1886, iii, 45, 862) regarded the peroxychromic acid as $4H_2O_2 \cdot 2CrO_3$, i. e. H_4CrO_7 with an anhydride CrO_3 . Carnot (*compt. rend.*, 1888, 107, 948, 997) found the reaction of H_2O_2 on chromic acid to be a quantitative reduction of the acid. Berthelot (*compt. rend.*, 1889, 108, 24, 157, 477) was of the opinion that two types of reactions took place when hydrogen peroxide was added to chromic acid, and when chromic acid was added to hydrogen peroxide. In the first case the reaction takes place as :

i. e., the chromic acid and hydrogen peroxide each loses the same quantity of oxygen. In the second case the reaction seems to occur in two stages :

and then

when 1.66 times as much of oxygen is derived from the peroxide as from CrO_3 . The intermediate Cr_2O_7 is considered to be the anhydride of the blue peroxychromic acid. Bauwann (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1891, 4, 135) confirmed the view of Berthelot.

A detailed study of the mechanism of the formation of the blue peroxychromic acid was made by Riesenfeld *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3380, 3578). According to him the reaction between CrO_3 and H_2O_2 takes place as :

with an intermediate product Cr_2O_8 ; which may be represented as

followed by

and when the hydrogen peroxide is in excess:

followed by

or else according to

followed by

Rai and Prakash have observed (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1954, 275, 94) that the decomposition product of the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid is chromium dichromate. Further, it has been observed (Rai, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 68) that whether hydrogen peroxide is added to the chromic acid solution or *vice versa*, the same chemical substance is formed, and the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid after investigation has been found out to be chromium perchromate and not an acid, and the formula suggested is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$. It means that chromium is present not only in the form of perchromate ion but also as trivalent chromium in the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid. This view has been further confirmed (Rai, *loc. cit.*) that the complexes formed with pyridine and piperidine with ethereal blue peroxychromic acid contain trivalent chromium also.

In view of the above observations an attempt has been made to suggest the mechanism of the reaction in the formation of the blue peroxychromic acid when hydrogen peroxide is added to chromic acid solution. It is a well-known fact that chromic acid solution is a mixture of H_2CrO_4 and $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, i.e., it contains CrO_4^{2-} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$. When hydrogen peroxide is added to a solution of chromic acid or an acidified solution of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions are oxidised by H_2O_2 to $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{2-}$, which may be represented

as well as H_2O_2 in the presence of hydrogen ions reduces $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions to Cr^{3+} , which may be represented as

Then the chromic ions, thus generated, react with the perchromate ions to afford chromium perchromate, which may be represented as:

This $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$ is soluble in ether and therefore can be extracted with ether from the aqueous layer. Since there is also CrO_4^{2-} in chromic acid solution, there remains the possibility of formation of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3$ due to the reaction between Cr^{3+} and CrO_4^{2-} . This fact has also been confirmed (cf. Rai, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 59).

According to the mechanism of reaction suggested in the formation of the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid, a very interesting point arises, viz., if to an aqueous solution of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ hydrogen peroxide is added, then $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ will be oxidised to $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{2-}$, and

now if to this mixture an aqueous chromic salt solution is added, the chromic ions and the perchromate ions should react to furnish the blue peroxychromic acid (the chromium perchromate) which may be extracted with ether from the aqueous layer. This mode of reaction in the formation of the blue peroxychromic acid has been experimentally observed, as when to an aqueous solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ hydrogen peroxide is added and then to this mixture a chromic sulphate solution is added, the blue peroxychromic acid is formed which is extracted with ether; its nature has been experimentally investigated.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

A 5% solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (25 c.c.) was cooled in ice and to this 10 c.c. of ice-cooled 20 vol. of H_2O_2 was added, when a black substance was formed. To this mixture various amounts of 5% chromic sulphate solution were added and the blue compound that formed was extracted with 50 c.c. of ice-cooled ether and separated from the aqueous layer in a separating funnel. A portion of the ethereal layer (10 c.c.) was taken in a tared silica crucible, evaporated to dryness on a water-bath, ignited and weighed. The weight represents the weight of Cr_2O_3 . Another portion (10 c.c.) from the same solution was taken in a flask and left for decomposition and then titrated iodimetrically against a standard hypo solution. A third 10 c.c. portion from the ethereal solution was titrated in two stages against the same hypo solution: first without any acid and then in the second stage with 5 c.c. of 2N- H_2SO_4 solution. The observations are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

5% $K_2Cr_2O_7$ soln. taken = 25 c.c. 20 Vol. H_2O_2 taken = 10 c.c. Ether taken = 50 c.c.								
Vol. of 5% chromic sul- phate soln. added.	Cr_2O_3 present in 10 c.c. of blue per- chromate.	Volume of hypo used in titrating			c+d/b.	c+d/e.	d/e.	c/d.
a.	b.	first stage	2nd stage	10 c.c. of decomp. product.	e.	f.	g.	h.
5 c.c.	0.0032 g.	2.40 c.c.	3.80 c.c.	3.00 c.c.	1937	2.06	1.26	0.63
10	0.0052	3.80	6.10	4.90	1903	2.02	1.22	0.62
15	0.0094	6.10	9.00	7.50	1607	2.01	1.20	0.67
20	0.0102	7.30	11.40	9.30	1833	2.01	1.22	0.64
25	0.0128	9.30	13.80	11.30	1804	2.05	1.22	0.67
30	0.0126	8.80	13.40	10.90	1761	2.01	1.21	0.68

It is quite clear from the above table that all the ratios shown there are similar to those shown earlier (Rai, *loc. cit.*, p. 59). Therefore it may be easily concluded that the blue peroxychromic acid prepared by either chromic acid solution and the acidified solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and H_2O_2 , or an aqueous solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$, H_2O_2 and chromic sulphate appears to be the same as all their chemical and physical properties are similar in all respects. Therefore it may be assumed that the formation of the blue peroxychromic acid may be due to the $Cr_2O_{10}^{2-}$ and the chromic ions generated due to the simultaneous oxidation-reduction of $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ with H_2O_2 . We may therefore safely assume this compound to be chromium perchromate.

Arguments can be adduced that the formation of the blue peroxychromic acid may be due to the acid generated by the hydrolysis of chromic sulphate and not by the chromic ions from $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$. In order to make this point clear, the $p\text{H}$ of the chromic sulphate solution was measured by a $p\text{H}$ -meter; a sulphuric acid solution of the same $p\text{H}$ was prepared and parallel experiments were done with H_2SO_4 of the same $p\text{H}$ as of chromic sulphate solution. The $p\text{H}$ of the chromic sulphate was found to be 2.5 and so H_2SO_4 of $p\text{H}$ 2.5 was prepared and the blue peroxychromic acid was prepared with $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution, H_2O_2 and H_2SO_4 of $p\text{H}$ 2.5. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Volumes of the materials taken are the same as in Table I.

H_2SO_4 of $p\text{H}$ 2.5 taken.	Cr_2O_3 obtained from 10 c.c. of the ethereal blue compound.	Hypo used in the titration of 10 c.c. of the blue compound.
Nil	0.0007 g.	2.1 c.c.
20 c.c.	0.0012	3.0
25	0.0022	4.2
30	0.0018	3.8

It is quite clear from the above table that the concentrations of peroxychromic acid formed with H_2SO_4 solution of $p\text{H}$ 2.5 are very much lower than the corresponding values of peroxychromic acid formed with chromic sulphate using the same volumes of H_2SO_4 and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ solutions under the identical conditions. It is of interest to see that even in the case of aqueous solution of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ without any acid, a small concentration of peroxychromic acid is formed. This is due to the slight acidity of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution. It is thus concluded that the blue peroxychromic acid of the concentration shown in Table I cannot be due to the hydrolysis of chromic sulphate solution, but is due to the chromic ions in the chromic sulphate solution. The weight of Cr_2O_3 in the two tables can also suggest the same thing.

It is of interest to note that in the formation of this blue perchromate, when to aqueous solutions of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and K_2CrO_4 , H_2O_2 is added separately, black compounds are formed in both the cases. But when to both the above mixtures chromic sulphate solution is added separately, the blue compound is formed only in the case of dichromate solution. The above fact shows that probably the formation of the perchromate ion is due to the oxidation of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and not to CrO_4^{2-} . For what has been observed, the blue ethereal compound appears to be $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$.

From this mode of formation of the chromium perchromate, it appears that by taking potassium dichromate, H_2O_2 and solutions of other cations, diverse perchromates may be prepared; but successful application of this method in the case of other perchromate depends on their separation from the aqueous layer.